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Daylight performance of an adaptive façade shading system integrated on a multi-storey office building

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Abstract

Adaptive façade design plays a key role in energy performance and sustainability considering the thermal, lighting, acoustic, and visual occupants' comfort as well as aesthetics, economics and durability. In this research, adaptive modifications have been conducted to an existing external shading system of a multi-storey office building. The considered design parameters are the orientation and depth of the shading systems, as well as the rotation, width and distance between the embedded louvers. The parametric analysis has been conducted with Archsim Energy Modeling and DIVA plugin in Rhino/Grasshopper linked with EnergyPlus simulation engine. The simulation study refers to Athens, Greece with typical Mediterranean climate set on clear sky with sun. Due to the south-west building orientation, four case studies in different point-in-time with four thermal zones demonstrate the illuminance. The analysis evaluates the effectiveness of the shading system according to the Air Temperature and Windows Total Transmitted Solar Radiation Energy. The simulation analysis indicates that the adaptive façade system provides an optimal and functional lighting for indoor comfort while preventing the façade from overheating. Future research refers to the optimization of the thermal performance and ventilation of the proposed adaptive façade system.

Key words: Office building, daylight performance, adaptive building envelope, optimization, kinetic system

1. Introduction

Building envelope design plays a key role in energy performance and sustainability considering the thermal, lighting, acoustic and visual occupants' comfort and well-being, as well as aesthetics, economics and durability. A brief explanation on indoor environmental quality based on these issues is presented in [1]. Numerical studies and assessments evaluate the performance of external shades with different strategies by scoping the impact of them with regard to the building envelope and the indoor environment [2-6]. Different typologies of shadings such as overhangs, vertical fins, horizontal shading, egg-crate shading, perforated screens and exterior blinds are giving potential opportunities for energy savings and improvement of indoor environment. Among the geometrical configuration of shades, several studies report the impact of slats' materiality. The reflectivity level of the slats concerning the indoor glaring and the energy needs for artificial lighting is reported in [7]. The effectiveness of external shading devices in a residential building is investigated in [8] in terms of energy savings for heating and cooling. A comparison of the thermal and visual efficiency of different types of solar shadings in non-residential buildings is studied in [9] by selecting the most efficient solar shade.

The sustainability role of the external shading elements can be further extended by means of adaptability [10]. In the light of the energy performance of buildings, external factors most associated with adaptability are the solar radiation and outdoor temperature [11]. Adaptive systems are further developed for their direct application on building façades, in order to provide control of natural light, ventilation and temperature of the inner spaces through their own transformability, surface openings and materials enhancing the end-users' internal comfort. Two representative built examples, the Arab World Institute and the Maison de Verre in Paris, are reconciling the changing environment and user activities through the automated diaphragm and mechanical adjustments [12]. The effectiveness of kinetic façades in terms of energy savings is demonstrated

in [13] with three existing buildings, Al Bahar Towers, Council House 2 and Q1 Headquarters Building. Adaptive folding shading systems placed externally on the Al-Bahar Tower in Abu Dhabi obtain different configurations, in order to regulate solar radiation and maximize the energy savings on cooling. In tracking the sun position, the kinetic system applied on the western façade of the Council House 2 in Australia provides full shading while minimizing the energy consumption by 85 %. Following the sun path with three different configurations by the motorized swivel vertical louvers of the Q1 Headquarters Building in Germany, the adaptive external shading system succeeds in minimizing the electricity consumption, glare, as well as maximizing the heat gain and natural air ventilation.

Adaptive building envelopes may provide a real-time process of reconfiguration enlivening the environmental performance compared to conventional static building envelopes. William and Thomas Zuk introduced the concept of lightweight actively controlled or smart structures, intentionally designed to accommodate varying user needs and external conditions [14]. In the context of utilizing and increasing the energy efficiency of the building enclosure, adaptive structures with active members may shape future activities in architectural research. The ability of constantly changing form following a closed-loop control system places adaptive structures at the forefront of the architectural design [15].

Adaptive façade elements enliven the environmental performance of the building and enhance the end-users' internal comfort. A taxonomy of kinetic systems is presented according to the system configuration (e.g. deployable kinetic structures, dynamic kinetic structure and embedded kinetic structures) and control techniques (e.g. internal, direct, indirect, responsive indirect and ubiquitous responsive indirect control, heuristic responsive indirect control) [16]. Controllable kinetic elements and responsive facades or structural systems are included in the subcategories of dynamic and embedded kinetic structures respectively. A similar approach assuming that the building envelope can act as living part classified four methods of actuation (motor-based, hydraulic, pneumatic and material-based) [17]. Typologies distinguished by movement of rigid and deformable building elements, soft and flexible materials, elastic materials and pneumatic forms are presented in [15]. A further analysis with key examples of the contemporary practice classifies adaptive façades according to the translation, rotation, scaling and material deformation of the kinetic elements [18]. The classification of kinetic systems in terms of environmental control systems is introduced in [19]. The proposed categories include the skin-units' systems (e.g. responsive/interactive facades, flare skin, movable louvers), retractable elements, revolving the buildings and biomechanical systems following criteria of kinematics, control techniques, system configuration, control limit and cost.

Relevant responsive systems meditated to sustainable issues, functionality and aesthetics considerations in a conceptual and structural design level are outlined. An experimental prototype in full-scale of a tensegrity structure is actuated in obtaining a responsive behavior through adjustment of tension members and actuators [20]. A conceptual development of an adaptable structure aiming at structural simplicity and reduced energy consumption during the reconfiguration is presented in [21]. The proposed actuation method conveys the ability to the structure to obtain different geometrical reconfigurations. The methodology approach of the responsive skylight modules leading to the integration of architectural kinetic elements and computational devices is presented in [22]. Design requirements of the project are the optimization of the thermal and daylighting conditions. The prototype system is based on tensegrity principles incorporated with photovoltaic panels in its structure. A similar approach on adaptive tensegrity architecture mimics the dynamics of a blinking sail as a dynamic sun-screen harvesting device presented in [23].

By extent, an adaptive shading system integrated in SAILS, a multi-storey office building designed by Agnes Couvelas, Architect, is taken as an example to improve the building energy performance with dynamic behavior over time (Fig. 1). The project called for the transformation of an existing warehouse into a four-storey office building with a single retail store on the ground floor. Sustainability was at the core of the project; both the bearing concrete structure and the building envelope were totally re-structured to address such issues as well as building regulations for the new use. The external shading system and vegetation regulate the solar radiation that affects the facade glazing areas. The open-space offices of the building are protected from overheating and glare in the summer while allowing light transmission. Shade elements also mitigate the traffic noise along the western artery and screen it visually as well as trap the fresher north-eastern summer breeze improving the interior air quality. Deciduous trees are planted on the ground, and plants in linear pots are provided along each floor of the south-west elevation. Geothermal energy for heating and cooling through a ground heat exchanger was provided, while natural ventilation and light were enhanced [24].

Figure 1: SAILS Shading devices, Office Building, Piraeus, 2014, Agnes Couvelas, Architect, and detail of the present shading elements.

In this research, adaptive modifications have been conducted to the existing external shading system of the multi-storey office building. The optimal daylight performance, visual and occupant comfort have been investigated following a parametric simulation with respect to the local sun paths, local climate and internal loads of the building. In order to minimize energy use for lighting, controlling glare and lighting intensity of the work surfaces, different configurations of the shading system and embedded louvers have been investigated. In a previous study of the authors [25], the daylighting performance of the adaptive façade system indicates that the initial configuration of the external shades, as well as trees and shrubs have a significant impact on decreasing the transmitted solar radiation and solar heat gain. The six curved steel standardized shading panels added to the exterior of the façade have been studied with twenty-four different configurations. Tube sections of CHS 114.3 x 5.6 mm comprise the curved end of the shading system, and the embedded louvers are made of natural wood, 32 x 60 mm, Fig. 1. The maximum width of the curved shading vertical panels on the first, second, third and fourth floor is 1.70, 2.65, 2.60 and 1.90 m respectively. Optimization and effectiveness of the external shading system may thus be obtained through its ability to adapt to changing climatic conditions.

2. Adaptive Shading System: The Mechanism

In order to create a comfortable indoor environment in the office building, a new adaptive shading system has been proposed, which can respond to changing weather conditions and occupants' needs. The existing sail-shaped frame structure on the façade has been kept (Fig. 2). However, the existing static louvers have been replaced with movable ones that allow adjusting the positions of the louvers according to the sun direction, in order to provide most effective shading. Each louver has been connected to the main frame structure by a kind of ring element that allows not only rotational movement but also translational movement (Fig.3). As demonstrated in Fig. 3, the revolute (R) joint at connection 2 provides a rotational motion about the pin axis that is perpendicular to the ring axis. By means of R joint, an adjustable position has been achieved for each louver.

As the R joint allows rotation of the louvers from 0° to 90° , the louvers can be used in any position. When they are used in horizontal position (at angle 0°) that is perpendicular to the façade as depicted in Fig. 4a, more daylight penetrates inside of the building. Natural ventilation can be also achieved by allowing air to flow in and out, if the windows are opened. When the louvers are tilted at an angle between 0° to 90° as shown in Fig. 4b-d, they reflect the sunlight, provide shadow and prevent direct glare. Because the louvers are adaptive, optimal configuration can be easily adjusted according to the position of the sun without blocking the view. When the louvers are parallel to the building façade (at angle 90°) as illustrated in Fig. 4e, solar protection is maximized. Moreover, direct radiation is blocked and the interior spaces are protected from overheating.

Figure 2: Adaptive shading system.

Figure 3: Connection details of the louvers.

Since the proposed shading system is capable of changing itself into multiple configurations, it is also possible to transform the louvers from an expanded form to a stowed configuration by cylindrical (C) joints that slide the ring elements upward as depicted in Figs. 3 and 5a. In this position, the view is maximized for the users. In addition to the translational motion, the ring elements allow rotational motion about the vertical axis. Thus, the louvers can be rotated to the left or right to obtain optimal configuration in response to the sun's position (Fig. 5b-m). The movement of the shading system is controlled by the linear and rotary actuators. Actuators can be operated simultaneously or optionally. Since there are six sail-shaped frame structures on the façade, it is possible to obtain numerous configurations on the building façade in response to changing conditions (Fig. 5). When the actuators are activated simultaneously, identical transformation behavior is obtained for each louver. On the other hand, when they are activated optionally, multiple configurations can be generated for the louvers (Fig. 5h). Compared with the fixed shading systems, the proposed adaptive system is capable enough to respond to changing conditions. It can significantly reduce the solar heat gain in the interior without blocking the view and natural daylight. By changing the rotation angles of the louvers, the quality of light entering the building can be easily controlled. Users' comfort can be enhanced by lessening the glare on bright days and maximizing the natural daylight into the building on overcast days. Moreover, the adaptive shading system reduces not only air conditioning loads, but also the need for artificial lighting.

Figure 4: Rotation angle of the louvers: a) 0° ; b) 30° ; c) 60° ; d) -60° ; e) 90° .

Figure 5: Transformation process of the louvers.

3. Daylighting parametric analysis

3.1 Method

The parametric analysis refers to the daylighting and occupants' comfort performance due to the shading system applied on the four-storey office building. The methodology focuses on the performance evaluation of the adaptive façade system in different states of reconfiguration in accordance to the design variables of geometry, position and inclination of shades and louvers respectively. A parametric model has been built, in order to perform the daylight analysis considering the vertical shades' and louvers' rotation, shades' width in each floor, louvers' inclination, section and relative distance. The analysis has been conducted with Archsim Energy Modeling and DIVA plugin in Rhino/Grasshopper linked with EnergyPlus simulation engine. The simulation study refers to Athens, Greece, with typical Mediterranean climate set on clear sky with sun. Due to the south-west building orientation, four case studies in different point-in-time demonstrate the illuminance, June 21st, July 21st, August 21st and September 21st. Four thermal zones are set in the analysis with maximum height, width and depth, TZ1: 5.25 x 11 x 25, TZ2: 2.80 x 11 x 25, TZ3: 2.50 x 11 x 25 and TZ4: 2.50 x 11 x 25 m respectively. The floor area of each zone is approximately 150 m² and the office occupation period is from

8:00 am to 6:00 pm, Monday to Friday. Materials and internal loads of people and equipment have been also included in the simulation analysis. Low E double-glazed panels with 0.50 transmittance define the glazing façade of the concrete building, while the walls and roof are opaque white elements exposed to the outdoor environment. Steel has been considered for the external shading structure and wood for the louvers. The ground floor has been considered as adiabatic. Sensors have been set at 0.90 m height from the floor in relative distance of 0.20 m. For a clear view of the adaptive façade system's performance, ventilation and HVAC system have not been considered.

Four different levels of modifications applied on the kinetic shading system address the daylight and visual comfort. Following the daylighting performance in previous work [25], two movable positions of the vertical shading system have been considered with $[5^\circ]$ and $[10^\circ]$. On the embedded louvers, a clockwise rotation by $[20^\circ]$ and $[30^\circ]$ is applied. In order to meet the occupants' visual comfort, a reduction of the shades' width has been regulated by 20 % and 40 % on each floor. The decreased shades width of the 1st, 2nd, 3th and 4th floor by 20 and 40 % amounts to 0.96, 1.44, 1.44, 1.76 and 0.72, 1.08, 1.08, 1.32 m respectively. The louvers' section and relative distance has been increased by 20 and 40 %, which are defined as follows: width: 72 x distance: 96 mm and width: 84 x distance: 112 mm. The configurations' notation is defined by [vertical shades' rotation] [louvers' rotation] [shades' width decrease] [louvers' section and relative distance increase]. This provided the opportunity to evaluate the influence of geometrical and topological characteristics of the shades, both with regard to the vertical shading system and louvers.

3.2 Results and discussion

Twenty-four configurations of the adaptive shading system have been systematically evaluated with regard to their impact in air indoor temperature and solar radiation on each floor. The criteria for comparing the assessment data are mainly the shades' solar radiation regulation, since this can largely influence the thermal and visual comfort, as well as the light energy demand that indicates potential opportunities for energy savings. To illustrate the performance of the different configurations, Figs. 6 and 7 show the indoor air temperature on each floor for the investigated selected point-in-time configurations. The outdoor temperature on June 21st, July 21st, August 21st and September 21st at 16:00 pm is 32.70, 32.00, 28.05 and 23.22 °C respectively.

Among the configurations due to the vertical shades' and louvers' rotation, and shades' width reduction by 20 and 40 %, the most affected floor with regard to the air temperature is the 1st floor on September 21st with a maximum reduction of 0.98 % in configuration $[5^\circ][30^\circ][20\%]$. This is followed by the 2nd floor on July 21st with a maximum reduction of 0.65 % in configuration $[10^\circ][30^\circ][20\%]$. In this case, the shade configuration of $[5^\circ][30^\circ][20\%]$ and $[10^\circ][30^\circ][20\%]$, result to a decrease of 89.83 and 87.22 % in solar radiation energy respectively, while the reduction of the shades' width by 40 % registered the highest values with regard to the air indoor temperature and solar radiation energy (Figs. 8 and 9). A noticeable increase in air indoor temperature is registered with the increased louvers' section and relative distance with a maximum of 1.15 % in configuration $[10^\circ][30^\circ][20\%][40\%]$. Inclination of the slats influenced mostly the configurations with a decreased shades' width and an increase of the louvers' section and relative distance by 0.98 and 0.93 % respectively. The effect of the shades may vary in each floor for the investigated point-in-time configurations with regard to the air indoor temperature and solar radiation energy. The maximum rate considering all the design variables with regard to the air indoor temperature is 1.15, 1.00, 1.05 and 1.20 % in configuration $[10^\circ][30^\circ][20\%][40\%]$ on the 1st floor respectively for all the investigated point-in-time cases. However, the outwards extension of the 4th floor influences the shades' impact on the 3rd floor with a minimum range of 0.03 %. The comparison analysis indicated that the configurations $[10^\circ][30^\circ][20\%][40\%]$, $[5^\circ][20^\circ][20\%][40\%]$ and $[5^\circ][30^\circ][40\%][40\%]$ registered the maximum rates of transmitted solar radiation energy. Overall, the results showed that the configuration $[10^\circ][30^\circ][20\%][20\%]$ registered the lowest values during the point-time investigated configurations in air indoor temperature and solar radiation energy.

Figure 6: Air Temperature on 21st of June and 21st of July at 16:00 for the investigated configurations.

Figure 7: Air Temperature on August 21st and September 21st at 16:00 for the investigated configurations.

Figure 8: Transmitted Solar Radiation energy on June 21st and July 21st at 16:00 for the investigated configurations.

Figure 9: Transmitted Solar Radiation energy on August 21st and September 21st at 16:00 for the investigated configurations.

4. Conclusions and Contributions

The simulation analysis conducted in this paper is based on the daylight performance of an adaptive façade system applied on an existing multi-storey office building for occupant well-being and comfort. The effect of external shading elements in indoor air temperature and solar radiation energy under unventilated conditions has been investigated and evaluated through the considered design parameters and daylighting performance. Shades with 20 % width reduction can control the amount of solar radiation and block the solar heat gain admitted into the open-space offices, while their impact on the air indoor temperature is significant by reducing the overheating and cooling loads. Different operative configurations allow the light transmission, while they protect the façade from overheating. The results indicate that rotation of the external shades and inclination of the slats may considerably influence the indoor daylight performance. A mixture of custom-made and standardized structures creates a contemporary sustainable building that embodies functional design and

craftsmanship. The innovative design solution of the adaptive façade system offers the opportunity for it to be integrated in different climatic zones. Consequently, adaptive envelope systems may even replace the passive function of double skin facades through regulated separation and active control of the effects of the external environmental conditions with regard to achieving overall human comfort in the inner spaces. Following their multi-parameters stimuli, adaptive envelope systems require a detailed monitoring performance data, in order to manage key challenges like dynamic and complex, intelligent and sensitive, unpredictable and fragile features [26]. Patterns of user control behaviour report that the building performance and automation systems could be improved by robust occupant behaviour [27]. As a whole, adaptive envelope systems should act in response to the multiple performance aspects by reconciling robustness, flexibility, adaptability, evolvability and multi-ability [28]. Future research refers to the optimization of the thermal performance and ventilation of the proposed adaptive façade system.

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